

The Emerging Themes of the Coping Mechanisms of Public School Leaders in Stakeholders' Convergence

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Abstract. This study explored the expositions of public-school heads in prioritizing stakeholders' convergence as building trust among school leaders, particularly in the Davao del Sur division; there were eight (8) public school leaders who participated in the study. This study made use of a phenomenological approach to extract the ideas of the participants. The virtual in-depth interview was employed to gather some information regarding their respective experiences as they prioritize stakeholders' convergence as building trust among school leaders. Using the thematic analysis, the following themes emerged: Negative perceptions of experiences in engaging with stakeholders, seeking participation and support consume time, and limitations and struggles encountered. The coping mechanisms of the public-school leaders in prioritizing stakeholders were giving importance to communication, strategic planning and involvement of co-teachers, and transparency towards stakeholders' convergence. The insights drawn from the findings of the study were that communication was essential for the success of PPAs and effective collaboration among school stakeholders. They may continuously be innovative in designing school programs that would be appropriate for the improvement of the school and learners. The school leaders may continue displaying effective communication with school stakeholders and maintain effective collaboration to address any challenges. Involving stakeholders as they build trust was an avenue to enhance their competency in being influential school leaders. This study may also be published in any respectable research journal.

KEY WORDS

1. the narrative exposition of public-school leaders
2. effective communication
3. collaboration

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1. Introduction

The importance of education in national development can never be underestimated. Education is a critical investment that can break the Filipino's seemingly endless cycle of poverty and provide the youth with more opportunities. However, Covid-19 slammed the door firmly shut on all aspects of everyday life and disrupted schooling globally. The pandemic has exacerbated the learning crisis for low-income and middle-income countries in Asia and the Pacific, and this will likely translate into a loss in lifetime opportunities and earnings. In just a few short months it has been shaking the very fabric of education. The implementation of the continuity of learning is a challenge to all schools. Our school heads during pre-pandemic have complex jobs and are vital in implementing a School-based management education system. It involved strategies, culture, relationships, administration, operational, and complex

decision-making. School heads continue to uphold the systems' principles and initiatives to ensure increased stakeholders' participation and improved processes which contribute to achieving a more effective education system. During the COVID-19 pandemic, schools and school systems are also responding to constantly evolving circumstances, the increasing complexities of the lives of those in their communities, and external narratives. In a crisis such as the one in which we are currently existing, perfection is the enemy of progress. In this disruptive and challenging time, school heads need to act quickly and be the first to move and decide swiftly, however looking at the welfare of the learners and teachers. School heads became at the forefront of "pandemic learning". School heads in Nigeria face a wide range of difficulties that have a significant impact on their day-to-day experiences running some of the country's top academic institutions. Their capacity to offer high-quality education is severely impacted by these issues, which range from financial limitations to inadequacies in infrastructure. According to Ogundele and Ogundele (2019), the lack of infrastructure makes it difficult for school administrators to establish an environment that is favorable for learning for both staff and pupils. Moreover, funding restrictions present a significant challenge for school administrators, who must negotiate these limits while attempting to uphold academic standards. Limited finance frequently causes problems with resource allocation and lowers the quality of education offered in Nigerian schools, as highlighted by Ajayi, Ololube, and Adedoyin (2019). Principals and educators have found it extremely difficult to deliver education to the last mile in Bhutan's remote areas. These challenges include issues about the environment, problems in the classroom, and administrative roadblocks. Similarly to, Indonesia has significant issues in the field of education, especially in schools situated in isolated regions where settlers encounter income inequality and gender imbalances (Brillantes and Nebria, 2021). The management of schools in these areas presents significant challenges for educational authorities. In the meantime, isolated areas persist in Pakistan, a developing country with several civic shortcomings, despite restricted access to education. Even with limited funding, the government has created last-mile schools to solve this problem and guarantee that all pupils in need receive a basic education (Deema, 2021). Principals, or heads of schools in Canada, deal with a range of issues that are reflective of the changing nature of education. The growing administrative load is one major problem that frequently takes away from their capacity to concentrate on instructional leadership. According to a 2019 research by the Canadian Association of Principals, principals devote more than 60 percent of their time to administrative duties like filing and following rules, which leaves them with less time for interacting directly with teachers and students (Canadian Association of Principals, 2019). The demands of addressing varied student needs, such as those of Indigenous kids and students with special needs, and the quest for inclusivity further compound the complexity of their work. Canadian Teachers' Federation (2019), principals usually struggle to strike a balance between promoting an inclusive environment and meeting the needs of a diverse student body. These problems highlight the variety of duties that head teachers have and the necessity of institutional support in order to allow them to lead successfully. School heads in the Philippines face a wide range of difficulties that have a significant impact on how they manage educational institutions. Their capacity to effectively administer schools and advance high-quality education is severely impacted by these obstacles, which vary from sociocultural issues to resource limitations. Inadequate infrastructure is a common problem for school heads in the Philippines, as evidenced by a study by

Elegado (2019). Many schools in the country lack basic amenities including classrooms, labs, and libraries. The provision of high-quality education is hampered by the lack of infrastructure, which presents serious challenges to establishing a supportive learning environment for both staff and students. Additionally, fiscal restrictions pose a significant difficulty for school administrators, who frequently have to manage scarce financial resources while upholding academic standards. According to research by Cruz and Cudiamat (2019), school administrators in the Philippines experience financial constraints that might make it difficult to allocate resources and jeopardize the standard of instruction given (Cruz Cudiamat, 2019). A Department of Education (DepEd) report from 2019 states that there is a scarcity of textbooks, desks, and classrooms in over half of public schools, which has a big influence on how schools are managed (DepEd, 2019). The administrative load put on school administrators is another significant obstacle. Their primary job of instructional leadership is sometimes compromised by the bureaucratic responsibilities and compliance requirements that often overwhelm them. This administrative overabundance hampers their capacity to concentrate on raising student outcomes and instructional quality. School heads devote a disproportionate percentage of their time to administrative tasks rather than staff development and instructional leadership, according to a 2019

survey conducted by the Philippine Business for Education (PBE) (PBE, 2019). In the Division of Digos, school heads encounter major difficulties in managing their institutions due to overlapping responsibilities. These issues are particularly evident when multiple tasks coincide with scheduled seminars, leading to divided attention and conflicting priorities. Moreover, financial constraints, stemming from limited budgets, further impede the effective management and operation of schools. This study's findings would benefit key stakeholders as follows: Education Program Supervisors would gain a foundation for creating supportive policies and monitoring systems. School Principals were better equipped to enhance curriculum and manage resources and would receive guidance on learning continuity plans. Teachers would use the study to adapt materials and contribute to implementation plans, while students were prioritized for continued high-quality education despite pandemic challenges. Future researchers would also gain valuable insights from this research.

1.1. Purpose of the Study—The purpose of this phenomenological study was to determine the school leaders prioritize stakeholder engagement, maintain effective communication, their coping mechanisms as well and their insights on stakeholder convergence.

1.2. Research Questions—This study sought to answer the following questions:

- (1) What are the experiences of school leaders in prioritizing stakeholders' convergence?
- (2) What are the coping mechanisms of school leaders for prioritizing stakeholder convergence and building trust?
- (3) What educational management insights can be drawn from the experiences and challenges of the school leaders?

1.3. Review of Related Literature—This section discusses relevant literature on school leaders' experiences in prioritizing stakeholder convergence.

1.3.1. Enhanced Communication—Effective school leaders adapt communication for diverse audiences, fostering cooperation through cultural sensitivity (Karki, 2020). Professional development is crucial for enhancing communi-

cation skills, conflict resolution, and stakeholder engagement, contributing to positive school climates (Berlinski et al., 2021; UNESCO, 2020). Early communication builds trust, reduces fear, and encourages positive responses to policies (Fernandez Shaw, 2020; Carvalho et al., 2020). Various communication methods, such as SMS and village loudspeakers, can strengthen strategies and reach under-resourced communities (Angrist et al., 2020; Karki, 2020).

1.3.2. Increased Support and Engagement—School leaders prioritizing stakeholder engagement receive better support, leading to improved student outcomes and community investment (Ogundele Ogundele, 2019). Strong stakeholder connections enhance decision-making and resource-sharing (Smith Jones, 2019), while open communication fosters trust, accountability, and school performance (Williams Davis, 2019). Engaging stakeholders also improves staff morale and creates a more motivated school environment (Brown Green, 2019).

1.3.3. Strengthened Collaboration—Stakeholder convergence promotes collaboration, shared accountability, and resource sharing, leading to creative solutions and improved educational outcomes (Williams Anderson, 2019; Thompson Green, 2019; Patel Kumar, 2019). Schools benefit from stakeholder engagement through increased buy-in and problem-solving capabilities (Brown Davis, 2019; Johnson Lee, 2019). However, time and resource constraints, along with diluted decision-making, present challenges in balancing stakeholder interests (Dimmock Walker, 2019; Leithwood Azah, 2019).

1.3.4. Coping Mechanism of School Leaders—School leaders prioritize communication and strategic use of technology to manage expectations and engage stakeholders (Ertmer Ottenbreit-Leftwich, 2019; Hattie, 2019). Effective leadership requires transparency, resource management, and stakeholder trust, while self-

efficacy and administrative knowledge influence decision-making (Qiptiah, 2019; Sinaga et al., 2019).

1.4. Theoretical Lens—This study can be framed as the tension between Maslow and Bloom, in which Abraham Maslow’s hierarchy of needs and Benjamin Bloom’s taxonomy of learning represent the importance of balancing physical and psychological safety with learning and academic rigor. In a time of global crisis, grief, trauma, and instability, we need to consider Maslow before Bloom (Doucet et al., 2020). We should foreground health, safety, well-being, and belonging first before curriculum, pedagogy, and assessment. Of course, governments and educators around the world are ensuring that learning continues during this time in ways appropriate to their contexts. They are also realising the important social and economic functions that schools play. Schools are meaningfully continuing the education of their students in ways appropriate to current circumstances but with fundamental human needs, compassion, and kindness at the forefront. At this time, more than ever, we must consider humans before outcomes, students before results, and well-being before learning. Supporting student and family well-being means providing clear communication to students and families about changing circumstances and expectations. It means taking on the mantras of less is more and keeping it simple regarding curriculum and set work. A distance or remote learning model is a time to reconsider what is essential in the curriculum, not to fill students’ days with work to keep them busy. Schools and teachers need to be realistic about the work set in a distance learning model, allowing time for well-being, standing, stretching, breaks from screens, exercise, hydration and nutrition. This means using positive pre-suppositions when communicating with students about their lack of engagement or School leadership during a pandemic failure to submit work. This is not a time for punitive

or accusatory approaches but for gentle check-ins. There can be no student well-being without teacher well-being (Hargreaves et al., 2019). Considering teacher well-being requires leaders to support teachers through clear expectations and structures that take teacher needs and feedback into consideration. In places where teachers are teaching from home, many have their own children learning at home. This study was anchored on state Leadership, a concept that has long been studied by researchers, and is a complex phenomenon. The complexity of the concept stems from the fact that scholars do not have an agreement regarding its definition. The scholars also note that authentic, spiritual, transformational, and ethical leaders all possess qualities such as integrity, concern for others, and role modeling (Schwepker Jr Dimitriou, 2021). More specifically, leaders exhibit compelling communication, practice role modeling, and prioritize altruism, but servant leaders prioritize the success of all stakeholders within an organization while ethical leaders focus more on compliance and alignment with moral standards (Lemoine et al., 2019). Leadership is a process that appears in a group and includes common goals and influencing followers. In research studies, leadership is described as a dynamic process, in that the periodic characteristics or behaviors of individuals who have characteristics of a leader make it difficult to examine leadership as a whole, and thus prevent researchers from reaching a common definition of the concept. Leaders prioritize moral management, and authentic leaders emphasize self-awareness and authenticity, as found by Zhu et al. (2019), a recent systematic review on contemporary leadership in hospitality by Huertas-Valdivia et al. (2022) reveals that ethical leadership has received limited exploration within the hospitality industry. Considering the unique nature of ethical leadership and its vital importance in the tourism and hospitality sectors, Huertas-Valdivia et al. (2022) suggest that this leadership construct deserves greater research attention in tourism and hospitality sectors, where the rising number of ethical scandals and related lawsuits is a direct consequence of its absence and inadequate implementation. Lastly, Ethical leadership has been suggested to be particularly relevant to tourism and hospitality due to several ethical issues and misconducts associated with these sectors (Eluwole et al., 2022). Prior research indicates that unethical behaviors in tourism and hospitality, such as giving misleading information, sabotage, overbooking, and overcharging, may negatively impact customer satisfaction and firm performance (Dimitriou and Schwepker, 2019). On the other hand, tourism and hospitality employees also suffer the consequences of ethical issues, as such underpay, long working hours, or irregular work schedules, which may result in burnout, insecure, confusion, and vulnerable feelings the employees (Schwepker Jr Dimitriou, 2021). Scholars suggest that these ethical issues can be addressed when the leaders of tourism and hospitality firms apply ethical leadership (Mkheimer et al., 2022) to become a moral role model for employees and create an ethical work environment where employees are treated with respect, credibility, and fairness. Transactional (bureaucratic) and transformational (charismatic) leadership theory are the theoretical frameworks for this study. The study was based on the two leadership theories That is, these theories begin with the assumption that an effective leader in any achievement context exhibits the behaviors that are most conducive to group productivity and group psychosocial growth.” (Kovach, 2018) that speak to transactional- and transformation- leadership theory. Transactional leaders earn leadership through normative rules and regulations, strict discipline, and systematic control. Follower obedience rests on rational values and rules and established agreements. Followers are limited to the obligations and controls set for them by the transactional leader. Coercive mea-

Fig. 1. Conceptual framework of the study

asures are clearly defined, and their use is subject to certain conditions that are already established. The technical side of follower skills has major importance and forms the basis for the selection of administrative staff. Capitalism encourages the development of bureaucracy; bureaucracy also exists in socialist systems. Leadership is empirically related to some of the similar related constructs such as transformational, servant, and authentic leadership, but argued that it is well distinct from these constructs (Kumar,

2019). Modern organizations seek explanations from academicians and scholars (Jena, Pradhan, Panigrahy, 2019). Organizations seek guidance to explore the factors that may improve the willingness and involvement of employees to realize organizational goals. In this age of knowledge, fulfilling the higher-order needs of employees is a priority, primarily realized through establishing trust among employees throughout the organization.

2. Methodology

In this chapter, we outline the processes and steps involved in conducting the study, including selecting the study’s design, identifying the respondents, and sampling method, choosing the research instruments for data collection, and delineating the data analysis process. The researcher utilized artificial intelligence (AI) methods to meticulously proofread this work during its preparation, explicitly leveraging AI to enhance the overall quality, coherence, and precision of the manuscript. This methodology is communicated openly to adhere to ethical norms in research, underscoring a commitment to the responsible use of cutting-edge technologies and acknowledging AI’s growing role and potential in professional and academic writing. It also discusses the research design used, the role of the researcher, the research participants, the data collection and analysis, the trustworthiness, and the ethical considerations. The three most common qualitative methods were participant observation, in-depth interviews, and focus groups. Each method is particularly suited for obtaining a specific type of data. Participant observation is appropriate for collecting data on naturally occurring behaviors in their usual contexts. In-depth Interviews (IDI) are optimal for collecting data on individuals’ personal histories, perspectives, and experiences, particularly when exploring sensitive topics. Focus groups were influential in eliciting data on a group’s cultural norms and generating broad overviews of issues of concern to the cultural groups or subgroups represented. The challenging aspect of the research is studying a person’s lived experience of a phenomenon in a manner that brings out its universal components (Neubauer et al., 2019). Phenomenology is the study of phenomena as they manifest in our experience, how we

perceive and understand phenomena, and their meaning in our subjective experience.

2.1. Philosophical Assumptions—The philosophical assumption was a framework used to collect, analyze, and interpret data in a specific field. It establishes the background used to reach conclusions and decisions. Typical philosophical assumptions have different types and are elaborated on below. Good research begins with the selection of the topic, problem, or area of interest, as well as the paradigm. According to Perera (2018), a research paradigm is a body of generally accepted beliefs and ideas among scientists about how problems might be identified and addressed. It was also a general theory or philosophy. Research paradigms may be called methods in which scientists address the three fundamental concerns of epistemology, ontology, and approach-related queries (Perera, 2018). Ontology. This part of this research study pertains to how the problem relates to the nature of reality. The groundwork for understanding the world in which we occur as people and as members of society is established by ontology, or the study of being. Ontology’s potency lies in its ability to reveal our understanding of reality by studying the true nature of things, substances, concepts, experiences, words, and everything (Sol Heng, 2022); thus, multiple realities exist, such as the realities of the researcher, those of individuals being investigated, and those of the reader or audiences interpreting the study. In this study, the realities of prioritizing stakeholder engagement were elaborated. In this study, I relied on the voices and interpretations of the participants through extensive quotes and themes that reflected their words and provided evidence of different perspectives. The participants’ answers to the study were coded and analyzed to build and construct the commonality and discreteness of responses. I made sure that the participants’ responses were carefully coded to ensure the reliability of the result.

The researcher upheld the authenticity of the responses and precluded from making personal bias as the study progressed. Epistemology. This refers to the awareness of how knowledge claims were justified by staying as close to the participants as possible during the study to obtain firsthand information. Epistemology, or the study of knowledge, received more emphasis in their rationalist society because it set out to explain why they jointly decided that certain things were true. Others were not (Sol Heng, 2022). I would identify phenomenology using thematic analysis as the best means for this type of study. In this regard, individual researchers “hold explicit belief.” This research aimed to gather essential details on the experiences of school heads in the Division of Digos City, Davao del Sur. I assured that I would establish a close interaction with the participants to gain direct information that would shed light on the knowledge behind the inquiry, particularly on the experiences of school heads in engaging stakeholders. Axiology refers to the role of values in research. Sol and Heng (2022) stressed that in philosophy, axiology was defined as a term that deals with ethics, aesthetics, and religion. In research, axiology was described as what the researcher believed was valuable and ethical. I uphold the dignity and value of every piece of information obtained from the participants. The researcher understands the personal and value-laden nature of the information gathered from the study. Therefore, I preserve the merit of the participants’ answers and carefully interpret them in light of the participants’ interpretations. Rhetorics. This philosophical assumption stressed that the researcher may write in a literary, informal style using the personal voice, qualitative terms, and limited definitions. In the study, the researcher used the first person to explain the school heads’ experiences and coping mechanisms and thor-

oroughly discussed their responses during the interview.

2.2. Qualitative Assumptions—The methodology was distinct from the method. Essence from a phenomenological research perspective or methodology is described as the intuitive structure of meaning, whereby direct examples build a complex understanding of an experience (Merriam Greiner, 2019). “This form of inquiry is an attempt to deal with inner experience unexamined in everyday life” (Merriam Greiner, 2019). In this study, the experiences and coping mechanisms of the school heads were unleashed from their narratives, specifically those coming from Digos City, Davao del Sur. The researcher’s drive-in knowing the deeper meaning of the predicaments of the physical education teachers became the basis for doing qualitative research, a means by which The challenge was to engage in the study of a person’s lived experience of a phenomenon that highlights the universal essences of that phenomenon (Neubauer et al., 2019), considered helpful in looking for “meanings and motivations that underline cultural symbols, personal experiences, and phenomena”. In other words, it was the study of the meaning these things (or phenomena) have in the minds of the audience they were studying (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023). The primary aim of phenomenological research was to gain insight into the experiences and feelings of a specific audience about the phenomenon they were studying. These narratives were the reality in the audience’s eyes. They allow them to conclude the phenomenon that may add to or contradict what they thought they knew about it from an internal perspective. Phenomenological research design is especially useful for topics in which the researcher needs to delve deeply into the audience’s thoughts, feelings, and experiences. It was a valuable tool for gaining audience insights, generating awareness about the item being studied, and developing new theories about audience experi-

ence in a specific, controlled situation (Dovetail Editorial Team, 2023).

2.3. Design and Procedure—This study used qualitative research employing phenomenology. Interviews were conducted with individuals with first-hand knowledge of an event, situation, or experience. Phenomenology is used in studies that aim to comprehend the fundamental aspects of a particular group of life events experienced by individuals. (Creswell Poth, 2018). According to Tenny et al., (2022), the study of the meaning of phenomena or the study of the particular was the precise meaning of phenomenology. Phenomenology’s primary goal was to accurately depict, as accurately as possible, the experiences of individuals involved in a phenomenon. The researcher utilized the phenomenological inquiry approach, concentrating on subjective interpretations and prejudices when examining the participant’s statements (Juma, 2023). By employing this procedure, the researcher established the overarching significance of the occurrence, circumstance, or experience and acquired a deeper comprehension of the phenomena. In this study, phenomenology attempts to extract the purest, untainted data. In some interpretations of the approach, the researcher uses bracketing to document personal experiences with the subject to help remove him or her from the process. One method of bracketing is memoing.

2.4. Research Participants—This study’s participants were eight (8) school heads from various nearby schools. The selected informants were from the Digos City Division, Davao del Sur. Qualitative analyses typically require a smaller sample size than quantitative analyses. Qualitative sample sizes should be large enough to obtain feedback for most perceptions. Obtaining most or all of the perceptions would lead to saturation. Saturation occurs when more participants are added to the study, which does not result in additional perspectives or information. Finding a sample that can produce comprehen-

sive and significant results while reducing unnecessary strain on participants and using finite resources, such as time and resources, was a challenge (Young Casey, 2019).

2.5. *Ethical Considerations*—Considering the nature of qualitative studies, the interaction between researchers and participants can be ethically challenging for the former, as they are personally involved in different stages of the study. Therefore, the formulation of specific ethical guidelines in this respect was essential. The relationship and intimacy established between the researchers and participants in qualitative studies can raise a range of ethical concerns, and qualitative researchers face dilemmas such as respect for privacy, the establishment of honest and open interactions, and avoiding misrepresentations. Every research project has to prioritize the protection of individuals participating by adhering to the relevant ethical principles. Since a qualitative study was so in-depth, ethical issues are especially relevant in this type of research. The current ethical rules for conducting qualitative research, especially when interviewing a vulnerable population of women, frequently focus on broad guidelines rather than practical application (Mohd Arifin, 2018). For qualitative researchers, it was of the utmost importance to specify in advance which data were collected and how they were to be used. He also stated that informed consent was a prerequisite for all research involving identifiable subjects, except in cases where an ethics committee judges that such consent is not possible and where it was felt that the benefits of the research outweigh the potential harm. A minimum requirement for an interview study should be that written consent is obtained from the participant after they have been informed, verbally and in writing, about the following issues: the purpose and scope of the study, the types of questions that were likely to be asked, the use to which the results were put, the method of anonymization and the extent to which participants' utterances

were used in reports. Participants should also be given time to both consider their participation and to ask questions of the researcher. In this study, the researcher would follow ethical considerations as part of the process of qualitative research. It was the responsibility of the researcher to ultimately inform the participants about the different aspects of the research in incomprehensible language. The needed clarifications include the following issues: the nature of the study, the participants' potential role, the identity of the researcher, the objective of the research, and how the results will be published and used. In the same manner, this study was submitted to the ethics committee of the Rizal Memorial College graduate school for verification and approval.

2.6. *Role of the Researcher*—The role of the researcher in this study was to attempt to access the thoughts and feelings of study participants. It involves asking informants to talk about things that may be very personal to them. Sometimes the experiences being explored are fresh in the participant's mind, whereas on other occasions reliving past experiences may be difficult. However, the data are being collected, and the primary responsibility of the researcher is to safeguard participants and their data. Mechanisms for such safeguarding must be clearly articulated to participants and must be approved by a relevant research ethics review board before the research begins.

2.7. *Data Collection*—A closely interrelated step in the process involves determining a strategy for the purposeful sampling of individuals or sites. Once the inquirer selects the sites or people, decisions need to be made about the most appropriate data collection approaches. To collect this information, the researcher develops protocols or written forms for recording the data, such as an interview or observational protocols. Also, the researcher needs to anticipate issues of data collection, called "field issues," which may be a problem, such as having

inadequate data, needing to leave the field or site prematurely, or contributing to lost information. Finally, a qualitative researcher must decide how he or she would store data so that they can easily be found and protected from damage or loss. In this study, there were seven steps in the data collection process. First was the site or individual; the participants were the Division of Digos City, Davao del Sur school heads. Second is access and rapport. A letter from the Dean of the Graduate School is given to the graduate student for the division superintendent's approval. A letter of permission for the Schools Division Superintendent, the school Principal, and the concerned school heads is prepared for easy data collection. The third was the purposeful sampling strategy; all participants have experienced the phenomenon being studied. Eight (8) informants were selected in this study. The selected school heads were considered individuals who could best inform the researcher about the research problem. They were also considered individuals who have experienced the phenomenon and can facilitate the collection of data. This system is called snowball sampling. The snowball sampling is a non-probability-based sampling technique used to gain access to such populations. The participants were purposely chosen so that the information needed could expedite the study. However, snowball sampling is appropriate for gathering the exact data to answer the research questions. The fourth is the forms of data, the process of collecting information involved primarily in the Virtual In-Depth Interview (IDI) with the eight (8) informants. The fifth was the recording procedures; a protocol was used in the observation and interviewing procedures. A predesigned form is used to record information collected during an observation or interview. The sixth was the field issues; limited data collection was engaged in this study. The last or seventh step was storing data, which suggested using the database to back up information collected and

note changes for all types of research studies.

2.8. *Data Analysis*—In this study, all the data collected were carefully examined and thoughtfully analyzed. The researcher first described personal experiences with the phenomenon under study. The researcher began with a full description of her own experience of the phenomenon. This is an attempt to set aside the researcher's personal experiences so that the focus can be directed to the participants. He developed a list of significant statements. He then finds statements about how the individual was experiencing the topic, lists these significant statements as having equal worth, and works to develop a list of nonrepetitive, nonoverlapping statements. The researcher took the significant statements and then grouped them into larger units of information called "meaning units" or themes. He wrote a description of "what" the participants in the study experienced with the phenomenon. Next, he wrote a description of "how" the experience happened. This is called "structural description," and the inquirer reflects on the setting and context in which the phenomenon was experienced. Finally, he wrote a composite description of the phenomenon incorporating both the textural and structural descriptions. This passage is the "essence" of the experience and represents the culminating aspect of a phenomenological study. Thematic Content Analysis. A thematic analysis strives to identify patterns of themes in the interview data. One of the advantages of thematic analysis was that it was a flexible method that can be used both for explorative studies, where the researcher does not have a clear idea of what patterns are being searched for, as well as for more deductive studies, where the researcher knows exactly what he or she was interested in. No matter which type of study was being done and for what purpose, the most crucial thing in the analysis is that the researcher respects the data and tries to represent the results of the interview as honestly as possible (Montensen, 2020). Document analy-

sis. Document analysis is a form of qualitative research that uses a systematic procedure to analyze documentary evidence and answer specific research questions. Similar to other methods of analysis in qualitative research, document analysis requires repeated review, examination, and interpretation of the data to gain meaning and empirical knowledge of the construct being studied. Document analysis can be conducted as a stand-alone study or as a component of a larger qualitative or mixed methods study, where it was often used to triangulate findings gathered from another data source (e.g., interview or focus group transcripts, observation, surveys). When used in triangulation, documents can corroborate or refute, elucidate, or expand on findings across other data sources, which helps to guard against bias (Frey, Bruce, 2018). Environmental triangulation. Environmental triangulation is limited only to those studies where certain environmental factors can influence the findings. This type of triangulation uses different settings, locations, and other factors, such as the time, day, and season of the study. The idea is to determine which of these factors influences the information received. These factors are then changed to see if the findings are the same. If the findings remain unaltered under varying environmental factors, the validity can be established (Naeem, Saira, 2019). In this study, such triangulation was used considering that the requirement, as mentioned, is the use of environmental triangulation best suits the environment of the research being conducted.

2.9. *Trustworthiness of the Study*—Trustworthiness was all about establishing credibility, transferability, confirmability, and dependability. In a qualitative study, trustworthiness is very important because the results and findings of the research study depend on the researcher's conduct. The trustworthiness of a research study was important in evaluating its worth. Due to the nature of the qualitative study, honesty in all the data and details is required. Trustworthiness

makes the researcher's study worthy of reading, sharing, and being proud of. Credibility refers to how confident the qualitative researcher was in the truth of the research study's findings. The researcher in this study believed that honesty in everything you do was essential to attain worthwhile success. The researcher has no derogatory records or administrative issues that ruin her integrity. Transferability refers to how the qualitative researcher demonstrates that the research study's findings apply to other contexts. In this case, "other contexts" can mean similar situations, similar populations, and similar phenomena. Confirmability was stated as the level of objectivity in the study's conclusions. Stated differently, this indicates that participant reactions, rather than the researcher's objectives or potential bias, form the basis of the findings. This means ensuring researcher bias does not alter the interpretation of research participants' comments to support a specific narrative. In this case, the researcher has carefully documented the material utilizing the audit trail, highlighting each stage of the data analysis to support the choices made. This helps establish that the research study's findings accurately portray participants' responses. Confirmability (objectivity) is the ability of a researcher to evaluate data without bias, including social desirability bias, which could be present from the moment a researcher creates and uses a tool. Reflexivity is essential for controlling this kind of bias (Nyirenda et al., 2020). Dependability is the extent to which other researchers could repeat the study and that the findings would be consistent. In other words, if a person wanted to replicate their study, they should have enough information from your research report to do so and obtain similar findings as your study did. A qualitative researcher can use an inquiry audit to establish dependability, which requires an outside person to review and examine the research process and the data analysis to ensure that the findings are consistent and can be repeated. In

Fig. 2. Analytical Framework of the Study

this component, using the database was very important in backing up information collected and noting changes for all types of research studies. All the data collected must be properly kept for future use as references.

2.10. *Analytical Framework*—The study’s analytical framework was based on Colaizzi’s seven-step descriptive phenomenological data analysis method, known for its strength and robustness. Colaizzi’s seven-step analysis method provides researchers with precise, logical, and systematic steps (Wirihana et al., 2018; Kwang-Ok et al., 2018). I observed several steps in conducting a thematic analysis. The first stage in extracting qualitative data for analysis from the tape recordings was transcription. This was done to gain greater familiarity with the data and deeper insight. I relied on my resources to do the transcription with the use of my personal computer and some reliable headphones. I spent several nights listening to the interviews to deepen my understanding of the nuances of the language and semantics of the participants. Practice varied considerably in terms of agreeing to conventions with transcribers. Some ne-

gotiated the layout and conventions required, including researchers who wanted the kind of detailed transcriptions appropriate for conversations or narrative analysis. Others were sometimes less directly involved and accepted the conventions generally used by the one transcribing the information. The next step is data extraction and analysis. I used manual techniques based on note-taking and summary while listening to the recordings. My manual technique usually included some process of verbatim recordings of selected spoken words. I selected quotations about central issues or when what was said seemed important or interesting. I used several different techniques as taught to me by my thesis adviser. I marked up transcripts with colored pens or sorted data by cutting and pasting. This technique was useful to me in the process of coding, sorting, and collecting data for interrogation. This technique was instrumental in understanding links and relationships between issues. All these efforts and procedures included saving verbatim spoken words from the transcripts, which could be cross-referenced to the thematic displays or the maps.

3. Results and Discussion

This part of the study dealt with the research questions and their answers based on the responses of the participants. The participants unfolded their experiences as they dealt with prioritizing stakeholders' convergence as one way of building trust among Davao del Sur Division school leaders.

3.1. The experiences of public school leaders in converging stakeholders. —

3.1.1. Positive Effects—Enhanced Communication. Effective communication is essential for public school administrators to effectively manage various stakeholders, including kids, parents, teachers, and the community. Carvalho et al. 2020 highlighted how crucial it is for leaders to create plans to improve communication techniques to encourage teamwork and raise student achievement. Fernandez and Shaw 2020) research, for instance, demonstrates how open and honest communication may foster trust and guarantee that all parties involved share the school's vision and objectives. This study emphasizes how effective leaders address issues and win over their school communities when they actively participate in two-way communication. For the participants, emphasizing the value of effective communication can develop the mindset and skills needed to navigate life's challenges with strength, determination, and optimism. The participant believed that instead of dwelling on problems, it is more beneficial to encourage a solution-focused approach. Helping individuals identify actionable steps they can take to address challenges and move forward is crucial. For leaders, communication is vital in articulating vision, providing direction, and fostering trust. It ensures that messages are conveyed accurately and that feedback is received and acted upon. In personal relationships, communication helps to resolve conflicts, express needs and feelings, and strengthen bonds. These findings are supported by Karki 2020, effective school leaders need to be skilled at adjusting their messaging to suit

various audience groups and considering cultural and contextual variables. According to their research, leaders who communicate in a culturally sensitive manner are more adept at interacting with all stakeholder groups, which fosters more fruitful cooperation and support (Karki, 2020). To make sure that all opinions are heard and taken into account during the decision-making process, this flexibility is essential. It is impossible to overestimate the importance of professional development in helping school administrators become better communicators. Berlinski et al. 2021 investigated how focused training initiatives might improve school administrators' communication skills. According to their research, leaders may greatly enhance their community interactions by focusing their professional development on communication techniques, conflict resolution, and stakeholder engagement (UNESCO 2020). With the help of this program, leaders will be able to manage intricate relationships with stakeholders and promote a welcoming and encouraging school climate Public school leaders can use professional development, cultural sensitivity, technology strategy, clear and transparent procedures, and technology to improve their communication experiences. Recent studies have shown how important these components are for developing trusting connections with stakeholders and creating a cooperative, encouraging learning environment in schools. By concentrating on these areas, school administrators can greatly enhance their capacity to oversee the interactions of various stakeholders and make a positive impact on their school's overall performance (Angrist, Bergman, and Matsheng 2020).

Increased Support and Engagement. The participants underscored the effectiveness of supporting and engaging in enhancing citation education. Through cooperation, instructors can share best practices, pool resources, and address common issues in teaching citation. This collaborative approach facilitates the development of comprehensive and cohesive citation education programs and fosters interdisciplinary collaboration. The statement underscores the profound impact that increased stakeholder support and engagement can have on the educational environment. When stakeholders—including parents, teachers, community leaders, and local organizations—actively contribute their time, resources, and expertise, they create a dynamic and supportive atmosphere that can drive meaningful change. The importance of school leaders' roles in encouraging greater support and engagement through stakeholder convergence has grown in recent years. Studies show that when school administrators put community people, parents, and teachers at the top of their priority list, they frequently receive better support for school-related activities. This strategy is consistent with research by Ogundele and Ogundele (2019), who show that strong stakeholder engagement can result in increased community investment in school initiatives and involvement, eventually improving student outcomes and overall school performance. Additionally, stakeholder convergence is essential to improving accountability and transparency in schools. According to Johnson and Lee (2019), involving stakeholders in school governance and decision-making procedures helps guarantee that school leaders are held accountable for their deeds and choices. This heightened accountability may result in higher performance standards and a stronger emphasis on serving the needs of the community and students. Research by Williams and Davis (2019) emphasizes the importance of effective communication in establishing trust and encouraging a sense of ownership among stakeholders, adding credence to the advantages of placing a high priority on stakeholder engagement. A more successful and coherent learning environment results from open communication between school administrators and stakeholders, increasing general participation and support. Strengthened Collaboration. When school heads enhance their collaborative efforts, they forge stronger connections with teachers, parents, students, and community partners. This increased synergy fosters a shared vision and collective responsibility for the school's success. School heads can more effectively gather diverse perspectives, pool resources, and implement innovative solutions that benefit the educational environment by working closely with all stakeholders. This statement highlights that increased synergy fosters a shared vision and collective responsibility for the school's success. School heads can more effectively gather diverse perspectives, pool resources, and implement innovative solutions that benefit the educational environment by working closely with all stakeholders, including parents. Patel and Kumar's (2019) research emphasizes how stakeholder convergence affects resource sharing and support. According to their research, schools that have great stakeholder collaboration are better equipped to combine resources and knowledge, which can improve educational initiatives and programs considerably. School administrators can better meet the needs of their students and community by utilizing the combined talents of different stakeholders, which emphasizes the need for teamwork in school administration. Stakeholder engagement can foster stronger collaboration and more successful implementation of school policies and procedures, as demonstrated by Brown and Davis's (2019) work. Their research demonstrates that there is more buy-in and support for new projects when school leaders collaborate closely with stakeholders. The importance of collaborative approaches in educational leadership is shown

by the fact that greater support frequently leads to more successful outcomes and more seamless implementation processes. Johnson and Lee (2019) show that putting stakeholder convergence first improves students' ability to solve problems. According to their research, bringing different viewpoints together through stakeholder engagement results in more thorough and efficient problem-solving. School administrators can now address complicated challenges more skillfully thanks to this enhanced collaborative environment, highlighting the vital role that stakeholder participation plays in promoting school success.

3.1.2. Challenges encountered—Seeking participation and support consumes time. As a school leader, one challenging job is to encourage full participation from all the stakeholders of the school. There is no guarantee for them to receive all-out support from parents and the community, especially if there is a challenge geographically and the inability of these stakeholders to agree on anything. Involving a large number of stakeholders can be a time-consuming process, particularly when they are geographically scattered. The challenge lies in coordinating efforts across diverse locations, which can complicate communication and decision-making. When stakeholders are spread out, achieving consensus becomes more difficult, as differing perspectives and logistical barriers may hinder the ability to reach a unified agreement. Engaging stakeholders is often challenging, as there is no guarantee of full participation, and school leaders must be resilient in addressing these challenges to secure their involvement. For stakeholders who are highly participative and cooperative, schools show appreciation through certificates and other forms of recognition, reinforcing their valued contributions. When stakeholders see tangible results and understand the positive impact on their children, they are more likely to remain committed and engaged. However, a lack of clarity and

transparency can undermine this effort, leading to decreased motivation for accountability and potentially lower response rates. Therefore, school leaders need to provide clear, transparent information about the school's needs and achievements. Participants highlight that stakeholders may not consistently follow the established safety procedures because they are not accustomed to practicing these protocols in their own homes. This discrepancy can create significant difficulties, as it underscores a gap between the safety measures expected within the school environment and the personal habits of the stakeholders. School administrators run the danger of losing their reputation and their capacity to successfully lead and oversee the school when they neglect to put openness first. According to Hoy and Miskel (2019), cultivating trust and respect and upholding solid relationships within the school community so depend on encouraging transparency in school leadership. Promoting openness in school leadership is essential for building trust, fostering confidence, and maintaining student benevolence. Concepts like teacher trust, quality enhancement, improvement, strict monitoring, accountability, transparency, peer review, and self-evaluation are common in nations that have educational solid systems (Gönülaçar, 2019). Principals of schools need to be aware of the thin line between supervision and evaluation. These results demonstrate how successful educational institutions' operations incorporate efficient supervision, trust, accountability, transparency, peer review, and self-evaluation. Hoy and Miskel (2019), open communication is essential to building respect and trust among parents, children, instructors, and school administrators. Teachers and staff may experience a decline in morale and job satisfaction when school administrators fail to communicate openly and transparently. This lack of openness may exacerbate students' dissatisfaction and disengagement, which would ultimately undermine the

school's efficacy as a whole. Diluted Decision-making. When school administrators must balance the varied and occasionally competing interests of several stakeholders, diluted decision-making frequently results. This dilution happens when leaders try to include all points of view, which could result in disjointed or inefficient decision-making processes. Day and Gu (2019) found that this difficulty is more prominent in complex educational environments where the convergence of stakeholders' needs necessitates thoughtful and deliberate responses. When engaging stakeholders, it is crucial to recognize that not all individuals or groups can be delighted, and attempting to do so may dilute the effectiveness of your efforts. Therefore, setting strategic limitations is essential. Focus on identifying and involving those stakeholders who are most aligned with the goals of the project and who have the potential to contribute positively. By selectively engaging stakeholders who are invested and influential, you can ensure that the plan's benefits are more pronounced and impactful. Spillane's (2019) research shows that the demands of various stakeholders often dilute decision-making in schools. School leaders, Spillane notes, frequently have to deal with pressure from a variety of groups, including parents, teachers, and district officials. This might cause leaders to make judgments that are weakened to strike a balance between these conflicting interests. This dilution may make it more challenging to build a cogent vision and may reduce the impact of attempts to engage stakeholders, which may hurt student success and school performance. Leithwood and Azah (2019) investigate how decision-making is affected by distributed leadership. According to their findings,

distributed leadership can increase stakeholder involvement, but if it is not handled well, it may also stifle decision-making. They contend that it is more challenging to accomplish stakeholder convergence when there are too many people participating in decision-making processes without a clear and cohesive direction. This is because there is a greater chance of competing priorities and diluted outcomes. The impact that relational trust among stakeholders has on decision-making in educational institutions is examined in Bryk and Schneider's (2019) research. Their findings suggest that weak, distrusted relationships between school administrators and stakeholders frequently result in weakened decision-making. Leaders may find it difficult to make choices that satisfy the many demands and expectations of their stakeholders in the absence of a foundation of trust, which could result in tactics that are ineffectual or inconsistent. Hargreaves and O'Connor explore how decision-making processes are influenced by the leadership style employed. They contend that because they must constantly negotiate and include the opinions of multiple stakeholders, leaders who embrace a more collaborative style may find it challenging to remain decisive. While cooperation can be advantageous for inclusion, if it is not handled with a clear sense of purpose and direction, it can also result in decision-making that is diluted. Figure 3 shows the Experiences of School Leaders in Prioritizing stakeholders' convergence and the emergence of the six themes: Enhanced Communication, Increased Support, and Engagement, Strengthened Collaboration, Seeking participation and support consumes time, Lack of Transparency, and Diluted Decision-Making.

3.2. *The coping mechanisms of the school leaders In converging stakeholders.* —The public school leaders would like to maximize and build trust in converging stakeholders of their

school who have a vital role in their success. These school leaders may experience challenges in dealing with time and safety protocols. They may be stressed if expectations and outcomes

Fig. 3. Experiences of School Leaders in Prioritizing stakeholders' Convergence

are not favorable as they strive to be influential leaders. Considering these barriers of converging stakeholders, there is so much to do and think about in maximizing the benefits and reflecting their learning on the performance of the learners, the achievement, and the development of the school. These problems never hindered the participants of this study as they gave their very best to cope with the glaring problems of the limitations and resources.

3.2.1. *Giving importance to communication*—When dealing with or converging stakeholders, communication plays an important role for the school to succeed. School leaders should keep them informed of the school plans and programs that can help sustain the school and achieve its mission and vision. Communication helps maintain good relationships among stakeholders, thus fostering trust among school heads. Communication constitutes a crucial factor in each organization. It has great importance for goal achievement in each organization as the persons involved cultivate a team spirit and unite their forces by communicating with each other. They obtain a common vision and manage their behaviors so that they correspond to their common goals. Participant shared that during our SMEA (School Management and Evaluation Assessment), stakeholders often

pose questions regarding the school's financial situation during our presentations. Addressing these inquiries effectively is crucial for several reasons. First, clear and transparent communication helps stakeholders understand the financial processes and decisions being made. This clarity not only demystifies the financial aspects of the school but also builds confidence in the management's capabilities. Effective communication presupposes an open communication climate that provides security to people and will encourage them to take initiatives aimed at improving the functioning of the organization. In this climate, the communicating members develop equal communication relationships with each other and learn to cooperate and understand each other. The principal of each educational organization, as the first among equals in the teachers' association, is a decisive factor in shaping a supportive communication climate (Brinia, Selimi, Kondea, 2022) Prior to the pandemic, evidence pointed to poor communication between parents and schools as a contributing factor to low student performance. In another low-cost text message intervention, schools in Chile sent parents information on student outcomes like absenteeism, performance, and conduct. After four months, students whose parents received the messages had significantly

higher math grades, improved attendance, and a lower prevalence of bad behaviors, and they were less likely to fail the grade at the end of the year (Berlinski et al. 2021) Given that the emerging nature of pandemic-related scientific evidence has contributed to mixed and changing messages, confusion and distrust among stakeholders can hinder the implementation of recommendations. Stakeholder engagement can be used to potentially mitigate this risk. Creating settings to allow education leaders, faculty, students, parents, and public health professionals to share evidence and rationale for local strategy selection and implementation (Hoover et al. 2021). Concerning decisions to reopen, education officials should communicate that schools are considered sufficiently safe in the face of the overwhelming benefits of a full return to face-to-face teaching coupled with strategies in place to reduce risk (Leask and Hooker 2020). A school in Colombia used a catchy mnemonic to remind students of handwashing, mask-wearing, and physical distancing and to avoid congestion, enclosures, and closeness.

3.2.2. Strategic planning and involvement of co-teachers—Effective planning should be established. Converging stakeholders takes enormous time, especially when dispersed geographically, dealing with different expectations, and the struggle on safety protocol, hence, the need for systematic planning, execution of actions, and effective evaluations of actions and outcomes. As a school leader, involving peers and subordinates makes the school goal achievable. Involving school stakeholders and keeping them updated will encourage them to participate and motivate learners. Effective planning involves anticipating future needs and challenges, which allows for the development of comprehensive strategies to address them. Engaging with technical working groups ensures that the planning process benefits from specialized knowledge and expertise. This collaboration not only enhances the quality and feasibility of the plans

but also fosters a sense of shared responsibility and commitment among all involved. By developing a comprehensive stakeholder engagement strategy, an organization can tailor its efforts to meet the specific needs of its stakeholders, fostering a collaborative and supportive environment. The sponsor plays a pivotal role in this process by ensuring that the concerns and interests of stakeholders are adequately addressed and integrated into the organization's plans and actions. When people have to deal with social issues and problems, social assistance plays a beneficial role. People who have strong social support networks will handle social duties more adeptly. According to Udayar et al. (2019), personality traits are reliable indicators of social support. These results highlight how advantageous collaboration is for both principals and teacher leaders. Principals prioritize developing relationships with teacher leaders based on trust, communication, and cooperation because these qualities create an environment that is conducive to the exchange of ideas. Higher levels of emotional openness, intellectual curiosity, liberalism, and an appreciation of art and beauty are traits of those with high levels of openness to experience. These traits would have a strong correlation with social support (Baranczuk, 2019). Those with varying degrees of personality features can benefit from social assistance in mitigating the high levels of stress in their lives. Modesty, obedience, and trust are examples of agreeableness traits that may help people create a larger social support system (Baranczuk, 2019). The traits of self-control, orderliness, dutifulness, and achievement-seeking are indicative of conscientiousness. These inclinations are favorably correlated with social support since they can assist people in managing stress in their lives. School leaders show a commitment to responsiveness and improvement by using ongoing feedback, evaluation, and adaptation strategies. This ensures that the needs and perspectives of all stakeholders are acknowl-

edged and taken into consideration. Schools create a culture of positivity and support that improves academic performance, boosts well-being, and advances the holistic development of both teachers and students by adopting social support leadership (Baranczuk, 2019).

3.2.3. Transparency towards stakeholders' convergence—Imploring transparency from school heads in terms of its strategic plans, school vision and being consultative through converging stakeholders. Involving the stakeholders signifies transparency among school leaders for them to gain support and assistance. As described by the participants, they all agreed that the involvement of stakeholders in school developments and keeping them updated is one mechanism and an effective way to achieve their goals. Keeping stakeholders updated and actively involved in school activities is essential for fostering a supportive and engaged community. Regular communication about school events, developments, and decision-making processes ensures that stakeholders are well-informed and feel a sense of ownership and connection to the school. Involving them in various activities not only helps in aligning their expectations with the school's goals but also encourages a collaborative approach to problem-solving and innovation. To

create a framework that directs decision-making processes, school directors must foster a clear vision and knowledge of the institution's objectives and priorities. According to Annisya, Susilo, and Sugeng (2021), this clarity helps leaders to make decisions that advance educational goals by enabling them to match their actions with the school's broader aim. Teachers will be more passionate about their work when they are involved in decision-making (Handayani, 2021). Participating teachers in decision-making also has the potential to boost their job satisfaction, which in turn raises educational standards (Rahmawati, 2019). For this reason, school principals must consult with educators and other relevant parties while making choices. Cross-channel communication is required for instructors to be involved in decision-making. Effective school leadership is built on the foundation of efficient decision-making, which is essential for navigating the intricacies of educational institutions and achieving favorable results for stakeholders and students alike. To provide a guiding framework for decision-making processes, school directors need to provide a clear vision and understanding of the institution's aims and priorities (Suryaniet al., 2019).

Figure 4 shows the coping mechanism of school leaders to prioritize stakeholder convergence and the emergence of the three themes: Giving importance to communication, Transparency towards stakeholder convergence, and Strategic Planning and involvement of co-teachers.

3.3. Insights are drawn from the experiences of School leaders in converging stakeholders And building trust.—With experiences generated from the informants of this study, it is inferable that there are mixed engagement experiences and perceptions of school heads

towards converging stakeholders. Leaders are faced with uncertainty and challenges of their knowledge, skills, and attitude in this difficult situation during the pandemic. Leadership is not a title but an action, a behavior, a practice, a way of being, and the current scenario has provided a crucible for the school head's agility, resilience, and innovation. Converging school stakeholders and building their trust is essential for the development of the school and most importantly its learners. Effective leadership fuels success among schools, their personnel, and the community.

Fig. 4. The emerging themes of the coping mechanisms of public school leaders in stakeholders' convergence

3.3.1. *Communication is essential for the success of PPAs*—Given the condition of a new normal and even for the newly installed school leaders, they are facing the monumental task to converge stakeholders through effective communication. Keeping stakeholders informed of the school programs and plans can help sustain these. Communication is an important ingredient and vital instrument in any given organization. It is how the organized activity is unified. It is the pillar upon which social inputs are fed into the social system. It is also how social behavior is modified and change is affected. Information is made productive and the goals of the educational system are achieved. A good school principal should bear in mind that the success of the school is determined by his effective management of the school. Seeking feedback on our communication methods is a crucial practice for continuous improvement and ensuring that we effectively meet everyone's needs. By actively soliciting input from teachers, parents, and students, we gain valuable insights into how our messages are received and understood. This feedback allows us to identify any gaps or areas of confusion and to refine our communication strategies accordingly. It is important to open communication channels with

teachers and teachers' unions, parent organizations, and other community groups to facilitate positive responses to policy changes. Communication efforts should match local norms and come from sources whom local communities know and consider credible. Word-of-mouth communication from well-respected community leaders and community members is still an important channel, particularly in areas with limited technology or limited literacy (Carvalho et al., 2020) In any organization, formal or informal, effective communication leads to effective management, which aids the achievement of organizational goals. Effective personnel management is a function of effective communication, as management involves working with and through others to achieve corporate goals. The realization of the goals of a secondary school as an educational organization hinges on effective communication among the various operating personnel. The basic function of education itself relies almost entirely on communication. A school manager cannot organize his staff, coordinate and control their activities as well as delegate responsibilities without effective communication (Ijaiya, 2000) The channel of communication needs to be modern, effective, and as personal as possible if management of large

organizations such as the school is to maintain close ties with teachers and encourage maximum performance. If the communication system in a school is open, an atmosphere of trust, reciprocity, intimacy, and growth is built thus giving room for effective teaching and learning.

3.3.2. Effective collaboration among school stakeholders—No one-size-fits-all, effective, and efficient way to achieve the school's goals and vision is through collaboration. School leaders should possess this skill of delegating and collaborating to succeed in school engagement. Excellent systems plan for leadership development plan for and develop their school leadership workforce and make an extensive investment in school leadership development programs. Embodying effective communication skills is crucial for fostering a positive and productive environment. Being an adept communicator involves not only clearly conveying your ideas but also actively listening to others. This dual approach ensures that all voices are heard and valued. Additionally, showing appreciation for team members' contributions reinforces their commitment and motivation. Building these connections sets a foundation of trust and mutual respect that is essential for a thriving school environment. By fostering an atmosphere where openness and respect are paramount, you create a space where everyone feels valued and heard. Encouraging active participation in decision-making processes not only empowers individuals but also ensures that diverse perspectives contribute to the school's direction and policies. The ability of school leaders to cultivate a pleasant school atmosphere and promote educational improvement is greatly influenced by their social development. Effective school leaders, according to Fullan (2019), must handle the complex social dynamics that exist in their institutions, including relationships with parents, teachers, and students. Strong interpersonal skills and knowledge of the concepts of social and emo-

tional development are prerequisites for this. According to Fullan, socially adept leaders can foster cultures that foster cooperation and respect for one another, which will ultimately improve the general school climate and academic performance of their students (Fullan, 2019). Social development makes a substantial contribution to school administrators' ability to carry out and maintain improvements in education. Leithwood et al. (2019) assert that a leader's social abilities are fundamental to transformational leadership, which entails inspiring and motivating employees toward a common goal. A culture where employees are dedicated to change projects requires effective communication, empathy, and the capacity to establish trust. According to Leithwood et al. (2019), social competency empowers leaders to meaningfully interact with their teams, which in turn leads to the successful implementation of reforms and innovations. Prioritizing social development helps school administrators better manage different school communities and resolve disagreements. According to Robinson (2019), the maintenance of a peaceful school climate depends heavily on the ability to manage varied opinions and resolve conflicts. Skilled in these domains, leaders can resolve conflicts quickly and amicably, reducing disruptions to the learning process and keeping the emphasis on learning objectives (Robinson, 2019). Professional development and growth are also impacted by social development, which plays a significant role in leadership. According to research by Kauffman and Ruhl (2019), school administrators who actively pursue ongoing social growth are more equipped to adjust to the changing demands and environments of education. They can lead their schools successfully and sustainably because of their continual professional development, which keeps them up to date on the latest developments in education and best practice. Figure 5 shows the insights drawn from the experiences and chal-

Fig. 5. The insights drawn from the experiences and challenges of the school leaders and the emergence of the two themes: Communication is essential for the success of PPA's, and Strategic Planning and Effective collaboration among school stakeholders.

4. Implications and Future Directions

In this chapter, the summary of the study was presented; from the summary of the findings, I drew the implications and future directions. The purpose of my study was to find out the experiences, coping mechanisms, and insights of school leaders in prioritizing stakeholder convergence and building trust, specifically in the Davao del Sur Division. To achieve the research objectives, I made use of the qualitative phenomenological method with the use of thematic analysis; through this interview approach, I encouraged my participants to fully and openly discuss their definition or meaning of the phenomenon being explored, which were the experiences of school leaders in prioritizing stakeholder convergence and building trust. Based on the results of the thematic analysis of the responses from the participants of the study, the following findings and their corresponding themes were revealed: the experiences of public school leaders delved into negative perceptions of experiences of converging stakeholders, seeking participation and support consumes time, Lack of transparency and Diluted-Decision making. The coping mechanisms employed by the public school leaders were the importance of communication, strategic planning and involvement of co-teachers, and transparency towards stakeholders' convergence. The insights drawn from the study's findings were communication as an essential tool for the success of PPAs and effective collaboration among school stakeholders.

4.1. *Implications*—The results of my analysis revealed the following significant findings. The pandemic has exacerbated the learning crisis for low-income and middle-income countries in Asia and the Pacific, likely translating into loss in lifetime opportunities and earnings. In just a few short months, it has been shaking the very fabric of education. The implementation of the continuity of learning was a challenge to all schools. Our school heads during

pre-pandemic have complex jobs and are vital in implementing a school-based management education system. It involved strategies, culture, relationships, administration, operational, and complex decision-making. School heads continue to uphold the systems' principles and initiatives to ensure increased stakeholders' participation and improved processes, which contribute to achieving a more effective education system. For school leaders working in these demanding and chaotic circumstances, the pressure is relentless, the options are limited, and the sleepless nights are frequent. Seeing to it that quality education was still delivered efficiently to our learners is something to work on in the new standard setup. The staff meetings, coffee catch-ups, and corridor chats with colleagues that made up a school day have gone. All those informal, important moments where social relationships are built, and leadership is enacted vanished overnight. Parents, students, and teachers now exist in the twilight education world, either awaiting the return of normal service or hoping for some new normal that might offer stability, continuity, and reassurance. The stark reality is that neither is likely to occur anytime soon. Communications around COVID-19 have been particularly difficult as public health and regulatory officials have had to make decisions and adopt policies while the body of evidence was emerging and continues to grow. For education officials, it has been essential to manage communication around school closures and reopenings, the availability of distance learning opportunities, decisions around high-stakes assessments, and other issues. Families are likely to be confronted with multiple sources of information about COVID-19 itself and its impact on schools. Clear and frequent communication is crucial to ensure that students and their families are well-informed and reassured. Transparent communication was also key for building trust between the state and its citizens, who were likely experiencing anxiety around the uncer-

tainty and disruption of school routines. Communication has emerged as a critical element of an effective COVID-19 response policy as school systems have managed school closures and reopenings for the year. This note summarizes good practice on how to communicate and what to communicate. The significant principles include communicating early and often using multiple channels, localizing communication efforts to involve community leaders, and ensuring inclusivity in messaging by using multiple languages and nonwritten modes. In addition to communications around health and safety, communicating to encourage learning continuity is effective at improving achievement in pre-pandemic settings. Opening feedback channels to hear from parents was equally crucial for planning. The coping mechanisms of the school heads are common among them as they maximize and build trust in converging stakeholders of their school who have a vital role in their success. These school leaders may experience challenges in dealing with me and safety protocols and may be stressed if expectations and outcomes are not favorable as they strive to be effective leaders. Considering these barriers of converging stakeholders, there is so much to do and think about in maximizing the benefits and reflecting their learning on the performance of the learners, the achievement, and the development of the school. These problems never hindered the participants of this study as they gave their very best to cope with the glaring problems of the limitations and resources. Stakeholder engagement can be used to mitigate this risk potentially. Creating settings to allow education leaders, faculty, students, parents, and public health professionals to share evidence and rationale for local strategy selections and implementation. Concerning decisions to reopen, education officials should communicate that schools are considered sufficiently safe in the face of the overwhelming benefits of a full return to face-to-face teaching coupled with strategies in

place to reduce risk. There were two insights drawn from the narratives of the participants in this study. The first one was that communication was essential to the success of programs, projects, and activities of the school. Based on the personal experiences of the participants, they were pressured on how to implement programs beyond the reach of stakeholders due to the circumstances faced. However, they realized that these were very helpful avenues to prepare them for the change in educational leadership. They observed that they became effective and resilient leaders, and communication among stakeholders was not that difficult anyway. They noticed that some stakeholders were just within their reach, just waiting for the school heads to communicate with them. Another insight that emerged from the narratives of the participants was effective collaboration among school stakeholders. No one-size-fits-all, effective, and efficient way to achieve the school's goals and vision is through collaboration. School leaders should possess this skill of delegating and collaborating to succeed in school engagement. Excellent systems plan for leadership development plan for and develop their school leadership workforce and make an extensive investment in school leadership development programs. Adequate leadership development and collaboration provided time for leaders to implement what they were learning and time for leaders to connect with key colleagues and stakeholders with whom they shared leadership and decision-making processes.

4.1.1. Future Directions—Based on the findings of the study, the findings must be properly relayed and used by the significant people

whom this research was intended for. The public school district supervisor. They monitor the programs, projects, and activities of the school and provide technical assistance for the future direction of the school. The district supervisors may further encourage the school heads to prioritize the projects of the school that provide maximum benefits for the learners. The school principals or school heads. They are more receptive to the current problems and issues of the classroom teachers, particularly the reading program of the school. The school heads may further encourage their teachers to consider that every teacher is a reading teacher. LAC sessions should be conducted to capacitate all teachers in designing reading materials in their field of specialization. The teachers. They may continuously be creative in the implementation of the different school-initiated projects for the learners. They should design a mechanism to address the pressing issue in the conduct of remediations. Stakeholders. They may provide support and engagements with the school for the implementation of school-based programs to enhance the abilities of their children. They may be an effective partner in guiding their children to comply and support all the activities of their children. The learners. To be more proactive in participating in the various programs, projects, and activities the school implemented for their holistic development. Future researchers. They may conduct the same study in a different location. Other leadership principles that school heads should practice may also be explored for the welfare of the learners, teachers, and the school community may be explored, not included in this study.

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